

MECHANICAL TESTING METHOD FOR IN-PLANE SHEAR PROPERTIES OF FIBER-REINFORCED PLASTICS

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1. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical in-plane shear test methods of fiber reinforced composite materials have not yet been authorized to date internationally, because of the difficulty of obtaining reliable properties by using simple and flat specimens under uniform pure shear stress. The first type for the in-plane shear test was historically a simple picture-frame loading fixture. Because of the nonuniform shear stress distribution accompanied with stress concentration in the test area in this original fixture, it was replaced by a doubly-linked pantagraph type¹⁾²⁾³⁾, in which the construction of rig and the forming of specimens were very complicated and the local premature fracture took place⁴⁾. And then, it was followed by the rail shear test or the off-axis tensile test, but there remains still many problems to be solved.

In the present paper, coming back to the previous single picture-frame fixture and improving it, the advantages and the usefulness obtained by its improvement are described. That is, it is proved by the FEM analysis that the nearly uniform state of pure shear can be obtained by the various revisions, such as movement of pin location, splitting of pin, insertion of plate between frame and specimen etc.. And hence, it is shown that the reasonable values of shear moduli and the higher shear strengths can be obtained in the experiments compared with the other various test methods, such as the previous picture-frame loading, the rail shear and the off-axis tensile methods.

2. SHEAR TESTS BY USE OF IMPROVED PICTURE-FRAME FIXTURE

2.1. Characteristics of Improved Fixture

(1) In the original standard picture-frame denoted as "previous" which consists of four-link frames as shown in Fig.1(A), the axes of rotation of pin-joints do not coincide with the corner points of test area. As a result, the stress concentration is induced at the four corners resulting in a premature failure as pointed out already³⁾. Accordingly, by moving the pins to the corner points of square test area as shown in Fig.1(B), the nearly uniform shear distribution can be obtained with lower stresses near the free edge corners without premature fracture.

Fig.1 Picture-frame fixtures

Fig.2 Compositions of revised fixtures

Fig.3 Specimens for picture-frame fixture

(2) A pin is splitted so as to be inserted from both sides of specimen without penetrating the corner area to keep it square. As a result, that makes it very easy and simple to construct a four-link rig and to cut off the square corner parts in a specimen.

(3) In this case, the inside corners of frames do not contact with specimen surfaces as shown in Fig.2(a). Accordingly, in order to avoid the nonuniform stress distribution around there, thin plates are inserted between frames and specimen, connecting them by small pins around corners as shown in Fig.2(b).

2.2. Verification of Merit of Improved Fixture by FEM Analysis

(1) Specimens used for experiments and numerical analysis

The finite element method (FEM) is applied to analyse numerically the stress distribution in the same specimens as used in experiments. The three kinds of carbon-fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) specimens are used as shown in Fig.3. That is, ① unidirectional one with $\theta=0^\circ$ denoted as "U0" ② unidirectional with $\theta=45^\circ$ denoted as "U45" and ③ cloth-reinforced one with $\theta=0^\circ$ denoted as "CO" where θ is the angle between fibers and frame edge. The thickness t is 3mm in consideration of preventing buckling and the edge length l is 100mm. The volume fraction of carbon fibers is 60-61% and the both sides of gripped edges are bonded with aluminum tabs of thickness equal to 1.5mm and then perforated together to squeeze by bolts.

(2) Effect of location of pin

The FEM analysis is performed in order to verify the validity of putting pins at the corners of square test area. The displacement of frame is specified by considering the rigid movement of four-link frame. The distributions of principal shear stress in U0-specimens with both types of fixtures are compared in Fig.4 in the case of corner radius of curvature $R=10\text{mm}$. In Fig.4(a) for the previous type of frame, a large stress concentration is seen at the square corners. However, in Fig.4(b) for the revised type of frame, the almost uniform stress distribution can be seen all over the plate even though there is a little decrease near the free edge corners.

(3) Effect of corner radius of curvature, R

In order to check whether the stress concentration at corner depends on the corner sharpness or not, the variations of principal shear stresses at both corner and center of specimen with the value of R are compared for both types of frames in Fig.5. It can be seen from Fig.5 that the high stresses at corners for the previous type do not decrease with an increase of R and hence, are not attributed to the small corner radius of curvature, but to the location of pin, and the stresses for the revised type are almost uniform independently of R.

(4) Effect of insertion of plate

The variations of principal shear stress along x-axis in both cases with and without inserted plates are compared in Fig.6 for the case of the revised frame. It is found

Fig.4 Comparison of shear stress distributions obtained by FEM in U0 specimen

Fig.5 Variation of principal shear stress with corner radius of curvature, $\tau_m = P/\sqrt{2}lt$.

Fig.6 Comparison of principal shear stress distributions obtained by FEM in U0 specimen $\tau_m = P/\sqrt{2}lt$

from Fig.6 that the shear stress distribution becomes more uniform near corners by inserting plates on both specimen surfaces and by connecting them with small bolts.

2.3. Comparison of Experimental Results Obtained by Both Types of Picture-Frame Fixtures

(1) Applied load-principal strain curves and shear moduli

The load-principal strain curves at center and near corner in U0-specimen with the revised frame(A) are almost the same as seen in Fig.7. The experimental evidence that the tensile principal strains are almost identical to the compressive ones in magnitude, denotes that the nearly uniform pure shear can be applied all over the specimen by the improvement of fixture.

The shear stress versus shear strain curves measured at center are compared in Fig.8 for the three kinds of specimens. In U45-specimen, the premature fracture takes place under small strain due to the tensile fracture(F_T) normal to fibers. However, in U0- and CO-specimens, the shear fracture along fibers(F_{LT}) takes place under uniform large strain without stress concentration at corners. The experimental shear moduli G_{LT} obtained in U0- and CO-specimens are compared with the analytical values⁷⁾ in Table 1. The values of G_{LT} obtained by the revised frame(B) are close to the analytical ones, but the previous frame(A) yields higher values because of the small shear strain at the central area as shown in Fig.4(a).

(2) Fracture behaviors and ultimate shear strengths

The fracture behaviors and the ultimate shear strengths obtained in the three kinds of specimens are compared in Fig.9 and in Table 1, respectively. With the previous

Fig.7 Load-principal strain curves obtained in U0 specimen

Fig.8 Shear stress-shear strain curves at center (revised fixture)

Table 1 Comparison of shear moduli and shear strengths obtained by various kinds of test methods and specimens (MPa)

test method \ specimen	shear modulus G_{LT}		shear strength F_s			
	(U0)	(C0)	(U0)	(U45)	(C0)	
picture-frame	previous	6210	7640	34.3	16.2	126
	revised	5020	4900	82.1	71.2	135
rail shear	two-rail	3920	4700	48.8	67.3	121
	three-rail	3820	5680	43.6	—	125
45' off-axis tension		3920	5590	48.3	—	110
theoretical		5290	5490	—	—	—

Fig.9 Comparison of failure behaviors in two kinds of picture frames

Fig.10 Rail shear fixtures with specimens

type of frame(A), the fracture strengths seem to be lower because of the premature fracture originating from corners due to the fracture mechanism of F_{LT} or F_T . On the other hand, in the case of the revised type of frame(B), the higher shear strengths are obtained with accompanying lots of failure cracks along fibers extending over the whole specimen under uniform shear. The above-mentioned experimental evidences show that the improvement of picture-frame loading fixture gives us the reasonable and useful fundamental properties under uniform pure shear, as predicted by the FEM numerical analysis.

3. COMPARISONS WITH OTHER IN-PLANE SHEAR TEST METHODS

3.1. Rail Shear Method

(1) Numerical stress distributions obtained by rail shear method

Fig.10 shows the testing fixtures and specimens whose merits are to be simple and economical. However, the stress distributions are not those obtained under pure shear, as shown in Fig.11 for U0-specimen, as an example. That is to say, although the distribution of shear stress τ_{LT} along fibers is almost uniform along edges except near free corner edges as seen in Fig.11(a), but the tensile stress σ_T normal to fibers concentrates at both ends as seen in Fig.11(b). This situation is a little alleviated by using a three-rail shear fixture, but is almost identical with those

Fig. 11 Stress distributions in U0-specimens obtained by FEM

Fig. 12 Shear stress-shear strain curves (two-rail, three-rail, tension)

$$\tau_m = P/Lt, \quad \tau_m = P/2Lt$$

mentioned above.

Since $\sigma_{T,max}$ at both ends is about one and a half times $\tau_{LT,max}$ and the tensile strength F_T is smaller than the shear strength F_{LT} , the fracture in U0-specimen is considered to be due to $\sigma_{T,max}$. Accordingly, the rail shear method is not appropriate to obtain the fundamental shear strength F_{LT} .

(2) Experimental results obtained by rail shear method

The shear stress versus shear strain curves obtained in the three kinds of specimens are shown in Fig. 12. It should be noted that the U0-specimen fails at smaller strain with lower shear strength F_S in the rail shear method compared with larger strain with higher value of F_S in the picture-frame fixture method as shown in Fig. 8 and Table 1. It seems to result from the fact that the premature fracture due to $\sigma_{T,max}$ at both ends as shown in (1) of Fig. 13. On the other hand, in the U45- and C0-specimens which include fibers besides along fibers, the crack lines grow all over the specimens under nearly uniform shear stress without much differences among various methods as shown in (2) and (3) of Fig. 13.

3.2. 45-deg off-axis tensile test

The tensile test of coupon with fibers oriented at 45° with the loading axis is sometimes substituted for a shear test as shown in Fig. 14. However, in this method,

Fig. 13 Comparison of failure behaviors obtained by rail shear method

Fig. 14 Stress components under tensile stress in unidirectional specimen

the tensile stress component $\sigma/2$ acts on the shear plane normal to fibers in addition to the shear stress component $\sigma/2$ along fibers which presents a state of combined stress rather than the pure shear. Since the fundamental strength F_T is smaller than F_{LT} , the tensile stress σ_T normal to fibers may thus result in a premature fracture. The values of shear moduli and ultimate shear strengths obtained by the tensile tests are shown in Table 1. The shear strengths F_s for UO-specimens are only about one half of those obtained by the revised frame fixture, suggesting the inadequacy of the tensile test method to obtain the fundamental shear properties especially of the unidirectional composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In view of the situation that no successful evaluation of the shear properties has been accomplished to date, an improvement of the single picture-frame are attempted in the present paper. The advantages of the revised single picture-frame are verified numerically by FEM analysis and experimentally comparing with the other shear test methods. The conclusions are summarized as follows.

- (1) The nearly uniform pure shear state can be obtained by improving the previous single picture-frame fixture which gives the reasonable values of shear moduli and the higher ultimate shear strengths.
- (2) It is simple and easy to prepare the previous single picture-frame test rig, but the premature fracture is induced by the stress concentration at the square corners of test area.
- (3) The two- and three-rail shear tests for unidirectional specimens are not adequate since the premature fracture due to the lower tensile strength F_T normal to fibers takes place at both ends.
- (4) The 45-deg off-axis tensile test by use of obliquely reinforced specimens is not adequate since the premature tensile fracture occurs normally to fibers under a state of combined stress.

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